

THE CONCEPT OF MEDIA, ITS LEGITIMACY, IMPORTANCE, MEANS,
FUNCTIONS, TYPES AND SYSTEMS

مفهوم الإعلام ومشروعيته وأهميته ووسائله ووظائفه وأنواعه ونظمه

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مؤخرة. أستاذ قسم علوم القرآن والتفسير كلية العلوم الإسلامية الجامعة الإسلامية العالمية للدراسات الشرعية والإنسانية

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Abstract

The study concluded that the media has taken a large and important space in the most prominent fields of contemporary life, especially open-source social media, and as long as most aspects of human, natural and cosmic activity; It was worth studying all their aspects to clarify the position of Sharia and the law on them and their rulings on them. There is no doubt about the necessity and necessity of submitting them to its means, functions and systems to ensure optimum benefit from them as they are among the services that are indispensable in our contemporary time. Accordingly, this study dealt with the issue of social media through the following images:

The first topic: the concept of media, its legitimacy, importance and pillars.

The second topic: the media, its functions, types and systems. Topics related to the media today are among the topics worthy of study and care, as the media occupies a large and influential space in various fields of life. Perhaps social media is one of the most prominent types of media in terms of influence and importance, as it is based on transmitting news and information from the community to the community itself, to achieve one of the purposes of news, guidance or guidance through its various means such as clubs, forums, places of worship, social networks, newspapers and books. The media directed to a particular place, group, or segment of society is considered its social media, such as the media directed to the community of a particular city or a segment such as women, or a group such as the disabled. Whereas the media and the press are of such vitality and importance; And I did in this subject as required by the requirements of the study. This study was based on the extrapolation of the issues in which the opinions of scholars varied according to the multiplicity of factors related to the edge, according to an applied analytical methodology.

Keywords: legitimacy, media, importance, function, systems types, means.

ملخص البحث

قد توصلت الدراسة إلى أن الإعلام قد أخذ حيزًا كبيرًا ومهمًا في أبرز ميادين الحياة المعاصرة خصوصًا الإعلام الاجتماعي المفتوح المصادر، وطالما معظم جوانب النشاط الإنساني والطبيعي والكوني؛ فكان جديرًا أن تدرس كل جوانبها لبيان موقف الشريعة والقانون منهما وأحكامهما فيهما؛ ولا جدال في وجوب وضرورة خضوعهما لوسائلها ووظائفها ونظمها لضمان استفادة مثلى منهما باعتبارهما من الخدمات التي لا غنى عنها في زمننا المعاصر. بناء على ذلك تناولت هذه الدراسة موضوع الإعلام الاجتماعي من خلال الصور الآتية:

المبحث الأول: مفهوم الإعلام ومشروعيته وأهميته وأركانه.

المبحث الثاني: وسائل الإعلام ووظائفه وأنواعه ونظمه.

وتعد الموضوعات المتعلقة بالإعلام في وقتنا الحاضر من الموضوعات الجديرة بالدراسة والعناية، حيث يشغل الإعلام حيزًا كبيرًا ومؤثرًا في مختلف ميادين الحياة. ولعل الإعلام الاجتماعي هو أحد أبرز أنواع الإعلام من جهة التأثير والأهمية، حيث يركز على نقل الأخبار والمعلومات من المجتمع إلى المجتمع نفسه، لتحقيق غرض من الأغراض الإخبارية أو التوجيهية أو الإرشادية عبر وسائله المتنوعة كالنوادي والملتقيات ودور العبادة وشبكات التواصل الاجتماعي والصحف والكتب. ويعتبر الإعلام الموجّه إلى مكان أو فئة أو شريحة معينة من شرائح المجتمع هو إعلامها الاجتماعي، كالإعلام الموجّه لمجتمع مدينة معينة أو شريحة كالنساء، أو فئة كالمعاقين. ولما كان الإعلام والصحافة بهذه الحيوية والأهمية؛ و قمت في هذا الموضوع وفق ما اقتضته متطلبات الدراسة. ولقد قامت هذه الدراسة على استقراء المسائل التي تعددت آراء العلماء فيها تبعًا لتعدد العوامل المتعلقة بالحافة وذلك وفق منهجية تطبيقية تحليلية.

الكلمات المفتاحية: مشروعية الإعلام، أهمية، وظيفة، نظم أنواع، وسائل.

The first requirement: the concept of media

To find out the truth of the concept of media, it is necessary to clarify its linguistic and idiomatic meaning.

Media as a language: If we look at the dictionaries of the Arabic language, we find that the media in the language is derived from the verb (know). It came in the tongue: "Knowledge is the opposite of ignorance: a man who is knowledgeable and knowledgeable from among a people, and a scholar and a sign if you exaggerate in describing him with knowledge, that is: he is very knowledgeable, he is said and he informed me of the news, so I informed him of it, and he knew the matter and learned it: that is, master it".

And in Mukhtar As-Sihah: Teach a thing by breaking it, teach it knowledge: that is, he knew it, and he taught him something by teaching, so he learned.

From the foregoing about the concept of media, we can say that its meaning in terms of language revolves around the following:

1. Telling.
2. Knowledge.
3. Education.
4. Transfer of speech from one party to another.

Idiomatically the media:

The media has been defined by many definitions, the most prominent of which are:

1. "What is conveyed to the recipient of news and information to achieve a communication that meets a societal need." It is taken on this definition that the scope of the media in general may exceed the scope of meeting societal needs in some cases.
2. The objective expression of the public's mentality, spirit, inclinations and tendencies at the same time." This definition is taken to refer to the state in which the media should have been in terms of neutrality, honesty, and standing up to the masses regarding what they tend to and want to see.

That is, the concept of media in the terminology includes all the processes through which information, opinions and comments are transmitted through the media, whether they are tangible such as television and radio, or intangible such as lectures and seminars, and the generality of what is related to the media. The intent is to achieve one of the purposes, such as informing, directing and influencing.

The second requirement: the legitimacy of the media

The media is as old as time. Since the dawn of humanity, the media has been present, circulating and common among people, as indicated by many Qur'anic texts:

حيث قال تعالى: (وَإِذْ قَالَ رَبُّكَ لِلْمَلَائِكَةِ إِنِّي جَاعِلٌ فِي الْأَرْضِ خَلِيفَةً * قَالُوا أَتَجْعَلُ فِيهَا مَنْ يُفْسِدُ فِيهَا وَيَسْفِكُ الدِّمَاءَ وَنَحْنُ نُسَبِّحُ بِحَمْدِكَ وَنُقَدِّسُ لَكَ * قَالَ إِنِّي أَعْلَمُ مَا لَا تَعْلَمُونَ) حيث أعلم الله -تبارك وتعالى- الملائكة أنه يخلق في الأرض خلقًا يفسدون after that: "I will make," they said: "Will you be placed in it" on the direction of seeking guidance and inquiring about this caliph?

As God Almighty said: (And when We said to the angels: "Prostrate to Adam," and they prostrated, except for Satan. Almighty - He has His angels, and prostration means: humiliation and submission, and his goal is to put the face on the ground.

We notice in the first verse that the information came from God - the Almighty - to His angels with the purpose of informing them about His creation of Adam - peace be upon him - as it came in the second verse directing them towards prostration to Him for His virtue, and both purposes "guiding and informing" are one of the most prominent purposes and goals that the media seeks to reach and achieve it.

In addition to these texts, the call to God - Blessed and Exalted be He - and the delivery of the teachings of Islam as stated in the Holy Qur'an and the Sunnah of the Prophet to bring people out of darkness into light requires the existence of basic aspects on which it is based, and in fact it is represented in the basic pillars of the media.

In addition, the Muslim is commanded to communicate his religion, and this adaptation obligates him to use the media within the framework of Islamic legitimacy. The bottom line is here: that through the foregoing, we can say; The origin in the media is the permissibility according to the regulations set by Islamic Sharia.

The third requirement: the importance of the media

After explaining the concept of the media and its legitimacy, we move on to talk about the importance of the media and its place in our contemporary reality. It is not hidden from the general public about the importance and influence of the media in various aspects of life. The media is the mirror of peoples, and their speaking tongue, through which they reflect their cultures, interests and aspirations, as well as enabling them to communicate and exchange cultural and knowledge with other peoples and societies.

With the rapid pace of contemporary life, the increase in information and the diversity of its sources, and the complexities that have occurred in life in its various fields in terms of time constraints in particular, and the inability to understand many problems and know the correct news and confirmed facts; Increase the importance of the media in general to overcome these difficulties, develop the ability to understand the human being and increase his knowledge of the surrounding environment.

And we are not exaggerating if we say: It is the king of the media today; The king of the reins of peoples and societies, as his influence permeates all aspects of life. Through the media, individuals and societies can be directed politically, security, morally, socially, practically and ideologically...etc.

To sum up here: the power that the media enjoys must be used positively towards the renaissance and development of society, and to push the wheel of progress and development in it by activating its many roles that it can play in various fields of life.

The fourth requirement: the pillars of the media

Before delving into the discussion about the rest of the media, it is worthwhile to first present its pillars, as no successful media operation can take place or complete with the loss of one of these basic elements:

1. The sender: He is the first party to the media process, and he may be an individual, as in self and personal communication, and he may be more than one individual or group, as is the case in mass and group communication.
2. The message: It is the idea, content, opinion or meaning to be communicated, and it is the essence and meaning of the media process.
3. The tool: This message must have a tool that it transmits from the sender to the recipient or the receiver. This tool may be natural, as in the case of personal and group communication, or industrial, as in mass communication that depends on the means and applications of modern technology.
4. The receiver or receiver: He is the one who receives the message, analyzes it, interacts with it, and is affected by its content.
5. Reverb echo: It is an important element of work The media mechanism and its success guide, and through which the communicative circle is achieved, so that the recipient becomes a sender and influencer after he was affected.
6. Impact: It means: the change that results to the recipient as a result of the sender's message.

The first requirement: the media

1. The means in language: all means, which are what draws close to others, and the plural of means and means, and they are basically what is achieved by which something is attained and by which one draws near.
2. Means idiomatically: In fact, when we hear about the mass media, our minds often turn to the mass media. towards television and radio, or media institutions and bodies, but this precursor meaning, despite its correctness, still falls short of explaining the true concept of the media, so what are the media then?

In fact, the concept of mass media is a term that refers to a form of messages that simultaneously reach a large number of recipients, including books, magazines, recordings, and films. That is, reach a large group of recipients simultaneously. The means of these messages vary between the visual such as television, cinema and theatre, the reading such as books, magazines, newspapers and newspapers, and the audio such as the radio, and their details will come - God willing - in the course of talking about social media.

The second requirement: the functions of the media

By jobs here, we mean what the media performs tasks and services towards the community, or the satisfactions and needs that are achieved for the individual and the community as a result of his participation in the media process.

1. Social upbringing: It is defined as a process of integration and interaction through which the personality of the individual is formed and reflects the culture of the community, if this is evident; The media carry out socialization in a parallel to what other institutions such as the family and educational institutions do.
2. Motivation or motivation: This is due to what the media provides of the reasons for honest and purposeful competition, by shedding light on the successes, achievements and superior models, and clarifying the factors and reasons leading to that.
3. Education: where the mass media work to spread and generalize purposeful human knowledge, which leads to the enrichment of minds, the dissemination of knowledge, the broadening of perceptions, the enhancement of human skills, and an increase in his ability to face problems and keep abreast of developments.
4. News transmission: It is a function through which a person is connected to the outside world, so that he can know what is going on in this vast world at all levels of his interest, whether at the economic, political, etc. level.
5. Discussion and dialogue: where the media contribute to the exchange of facts necessary to communicate different points of view on public issues, and to provide the appropriate and required evidence to support better interest and participation in matters of concern to everyone, whether at the local, national or global level.
6. Entertainment: where the media works to alleviate the suffering, tension and anxiety that a person feels as a result of the increasing pressures of life, by showing films, plays, series, parties, sports, etc. for the purpose of entertainment and entertainment for the public.

The third requirement: types of media

The media has many types or branches, most notably:

1. Political media: This type is concerned with the general political affairs of the state and its relations with other states. It also defines the state's political positions towards domestic and foreign issues, and covers political events.
2. Economic media: In its content and audience, this type of media is oriented towards the economic and financial aspects of the state such as policies, plans, budgets, agreements, problems and relations with other countries in this field. It also tends towards individuals and institutions in terms of capital movement, investment fields, and profit and loss indicators in the capital markets. Stock markets and other economic, financial and investment matters.
3. Developmental media: This type is concerned with the various developmental aspects that the state wishes to launch and introduce the public to such as the plans for political, economic, environmental and educational development, and to direct the public to absorb and participate in those plans.
4. Educational media: Its mission is to disseminate news, directions, information and ideas that help in dealing with educational aspects, issues and problems in the community, as it affects the educational and educational function that benefits students of science and is performed by teachers and supervised by the competent ministry.
5. Scientific media: It means this type of media about science and its issues. It monitors its developments and developments, addresses scientific and technical problems, discusses issues, and nourishes the community and its members by spreading the culture of science and knowledge through media materials that help it achieve its goal.
6. Security media: Its mission is to serve security issues and issues, and it aims at the supremacy of security in society, using all media and visual arts, and based on information and facts that are presented objectively to prevent crime or reduce it through legal, legal, psychological, mental and societal awareness.

These are the most prominent types of media, and it was found by those who reviewed them that the type of media is determined, varied, and divided according to its contents, goals, objectives and functions.

Fourth requirement: media systems

1. The concept of media systems:

The concept of media systems for specialists and researchers refers to social, economic and political ideologies and beliefs that research the elements and foundations of the communication process (sender, message, etc.), and policies of control, control and media censorship.

2. Media Systems Sections:

Media systems can be divided into three sections as follows:

Section One - Media Systems in Totalitarian Societies:

The systems in these societies vary in terms of allowing citizens to participate in the media process, and owning these means between absolute zero and conditional permission to be subject to state censorship.

Section Two - Media Systems in Democratic Societies e:

These systems allow citizens the freedom to participate in the media process and own its means, and consider that society must be a free market for ideas and trends, and what is bad will become lazy and will wither away.

Section Three - The Media System in the Muslim Society:

This system allows the individual and society freedom of expression and liberation, and gives freedom to individuals, institutions and the government the right to own and manage the media, but within the limits guaranteed by Islamic Sharia.

Conclusion

The current study reached a number of results, which are:

1. The numerous international conventions and recommendations are evidence and presumption of the international legislator's interest in the category of journalists and media work, and there has been remarkable success in unifying the professional work rules for journalists and media professionals, which were able to include protection and immunity for the journalist and succeeded in keeping pace with him in all stages of his work, starting from receiving information until publishing it to public opinion. And her success in moving it.
2. The rapid development of the mass media in terms of quantity, quality and influence is supposed to increase the interest of the international legislator in the situation of journalists in all aspects surrounding their work in order to work on legalizing them and determining their duties and rights.
3. The sum of international conventions and recommendations on the media and the press attests to the interest of the international legislator in the category of media professionals and journalists.
4. The relative and remarkable success in protecting media and journalistic work in various countries of the world was achieved through unifying the professional work rules for media professionals and journalists, including protection and keeping pace with all stages of media and journalistic work, starting from receiving information and ending with its dissemination to public opinion.

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Ayesh, Husam Khalil (1428 A.H. - 2007 A.D.) The Media: Its Legal Controls and Provisions (Unpublished Master's Thesis), The Islamic University, Gaza, p. 5.

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It is the modern means by which messages can be directed to the masses, and through which ideas, opinions and information can be communicated to an audience. These media may be printed such as: newspapers, books, pamphlets, pictures and drawings, or audio such as radio, or audio-visual such as cinema, or comprehensive such as the Internet.

See: Al-Zaidi, Taha Ahmed, Dictionary of Terms of Da`wah and Islamic Media (1430 AH - 2010 AD), Dar Al-Nafais, 1st Edition, Amman - Jordan, p. 276.

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Abu Samra, Muhammad, Media and the Three Powers, 1st Edition, Dar Al Raya: Amman, p. 54, Al Mashaqah, Media Theories, previous reference, p. 63.

Al-Joshan, Baraka Bin Zamil, (2005), Arab Security Media, Naif Arab University for Security Sciences, p. 5.

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This term means: every society governed by a system that does not recognize democracy, does not adopt the principle of separation of powers, and includes all dictatorial regimes, and many other definitions. See: Al-Khatib, Ahmad (1426 AH - 2005 AD), The Totalitarian System and the Islamic System of Government, Al-Wa'i Magazine, Issue 221, Issue 221 - Year 19, Jumada al-Akhirah, 1426 AH - July 2005 AD. al-waie.org/archives/article/3398.

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Democracy: means the rule of the people, and it is a peaceful process of the transfer of power between individuals or groups, and leads to the creation of a social system that adheres to the freedom of the individual, the sovereignty of the people, legal equality, partisan pluralism, political participation, the peaceful transfer of power and free elections.

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